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Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions

It decreased on average by 19.33%

Istat-Bes calculates the value of sedentary lifestyle in Italian regions. Sedentarity is defined as the standardized proportion of 14-year-old people who do not practice any physical activity on the total of 14 years and more. The available data refer to the period between 2005 and 2020.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of sedentary lifestyle in 2020. Sicily is in the first place for the value of sedentary lifestyle with a value equal to 56.6, followed by Campania with a value of 56.2 and Calabria with a value of 49.6. In the middle of the standings there are Lazio with a value equal to 32.7, followed by Sardinia with a value of 31 and by the Marche and Piedmont with a value of 28.9. Liguria close the ranking with a value of 22.2 units, followed by Veneto with a value of 19.8 and Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of 15.

Ranking of the Regions by percentage variation of sedentary lifestyle in the period between 2005 and 2020. Campania is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of sedentary lifestyle between 2005 and 2020 with a value equal to -1.58% equal to -0.90 units, followed by Sicily with a value equal to -9.58% equal to -6.00 unit, Calabria with a percentage variation of -12.52% equivalent to an amount of 7.10 units. In the middle of the standings there are Molise with a variation equal to an amount of -20.39% equivalent to an amount of -10.50 unit, followed by Emilia Romagna with a value equal to -21.00% equal to an amount of -6.70 units, followed by Lombardy with a variation equal to an amount of -21.14% equal to a value of -6.70 units. The Aosta Valley close the ranking with a variation of -34.18% equal to a variation of -13.40 units, followed by Sardinia with a variation of -35.55% equal to an amount of -17.10 Unit, and from Liguria with a variation of -46.38% equal to an amount of -19.20 units.

Italian macro-regions. Sedentarity has decreased in all Italian macro-regions. In northern Italy, sedentary lifestyle decreased from an amount of 31.20 in 2005 up to a value of 24.10 units in 2020 or a reduction equal to an amount of -7.10 units equal to a value of -22.76%. In Central Italy, sedentary lifestyle decreased from an amount of 40.20 units up to a value of 30.20 units or equal to a variation of -10.00 units equal to a variation of -24.88%. The sedentary lifestyle decreased in the South from an amount of 56.40 up to a value of 49.10 units or open to a variation of -7.30 units equal to a variation of -12.94%. Overall, in Italy, sedentary lifestyle has decreased from an amount of 41,90 units up to a value of 33.80 units or equal to a value of -8.10 units equal to a variation of -19.33%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized through the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm. The application of the silhouette coefficient is possible to identify the existence of two different Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Calabria, Puglia, Campania, Basilicata, Sicily, Molise, Lazio, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Emilia-Romagna, Lombardy, Piedmont, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Valle d'Aosta, Veneto, Tuscany, Marche, Trentino-Alto Adige, Liguria, Umbria, Sardinia.

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It therefore derives a median value of sedentary lifestyle which in cluster 1 is equal to 44.3 and instead in the Cluster 2 equal to 25.5 units. It therefore derives the following order of the clusters or: $C1 = 44.3 > C2 = 25.5$ units. In the contrast between the two Clusters, the distinction between a southern Italy characterized by a high level of sedentary lifestyle and a center-north Italy with a value of sedentary lifestyle equal to about 73% more than the value of the Cluster 2. This distinction puts is evident. In evidence, a contrast between individual behaviors that can also be in some way connected to profitability and the possibilities of life.

Network Analysis with Manhattan's distance method. A Network Analysis is created below through the application of the Manhattan distance method. Through this analysis, two network structures are identified, one of which is complex and the other is simplified. The complex network structure consists of Tuscany, Lombardy, Piedmont, Emilia-Romagna, and Friuli-Venezia Giulia. This structure is indicated below or:

- Tuscany has a link with Lombardy for a value of 0.76 units;
- Lombardy has a link with Piedmont having a value of 0.56 units, with Tuscany with a value of 0.76 and with Emilia-Romagna with a value of 0.39 units;
- Piedmont has a link with Lombardy for a value of 0.56 units and with Emilia-Romagna with a value of 0.54 units;
- Emilia-Romagna has a link with Friuli-Venezia Giulia having a value of 0.75 units, with Piedmont with a value of 0.54 and with Lombardy with a value of 0.39 units;
- Friuli-Venezia Giulia has a link with Emilia-Romagna with a value of 0.75 units.

There is a simplified link consisting of a biunivocal relationship between Basilicata and Molise with a connection value of 0.72.

Machine learning and predictions. A prediction activity was carried out below using eight Machine Learning algorithms. The algorithms were compared on the basis of their ability to maximize the r-Squared and to minimize the mean absolute error, the mean squared error, and the root mean squared error. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the available data while the remaining 30% was used for the actual prediction. The following system of algorithms is thus determined or:

- Tree regression ensemble with a payoff value of 4;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression with a payoff value of 8;
- Ann-MLP with a payoff value of 12;
- PNN and Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 18;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 24;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 32.

Therefore, by applying the best performing algorithm it is possible to predict the trend of sedentary lifestyle in the following regions or:

- Valle d'Aosta with a variation from an amount of 25.80 units up to a value of 25.36 units with an absolute variation of -0.44 units and a percentage variation equal to a value of -1.70% ;
- Lombardy with an increased variation from an amount of 25.00 units up to a value of 25.17 units or equal to a variation of 0.17 units equal to an amount of 0.69%;
- Veneto with an increased variation from an amount of 19.80 units up to a value of 23.43 units or equal to a variation of 3.63 units equal to a variation of 18.33%;

- Emilia -Romagna with a diminutive variation from a variation of 25.20 units up to a value of 24.99 units or equal to a variation of -0.21 units equal to a variation of -0.82%;
- Campania with a diminutive variation from an amount of 56.20 units up to a variation of 44.76 units or equal to a variation of -11.44 units equal to an amount of -20.36%;
- Sicily with a diminutive variation from an amount of 56.60 units up to a value of 44.76 units or equal to a variation of -11.84 units equal to an amount of -20.92%.

Overall, the algorithm predicts an average reduction of sedentary lifestyle from an amount of 34.77 units up to a value of 31.41 units or equal to a variation of -3.35 units equal to a value of -9.65%.

Conclusions. The data show a significant reduction in sedentary lifestyle in the Italian regions between 2005 and 2020. Specifically on average in Italy there was a reduction of -19.33% of sedentary lifestyle. However, the data show that sedentary lifestyle is still very present in the southern regions. In Sicily, Campania and Calabria half of the population is sedentary. It is likely that there are income problems that make the culture of sport and physical activity difficult. In this sense, it is necessary to underline that these areas are also generally equipped with a lower equipment of sports facilities than in the center north. In this sense, the investment in sports infrastructures, such as sports buildings, gyms, etc., and support for the sports association system could significantly contribute to a reduction in sedentarism in the southern regions of Italy.

Declarations

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Appendix

Sedentarietà nelle Regioni Italiane		
Rank	Regione	2020
1	Sicilia	★ 56,6
2	Campania	★ 56,2
3	Calabria	★ 49,6
4	Basilicata	★ 46,4
5	Puglia	★ 42,2
6	Molise	★ 41
7	Abruzzo	★ 34,6
8	Umbria	★ 33,4
9	Lazio	★ 32,7
10	Sardegna	★ 31
11	Piemonte	★ 28,9
11	Marche	★ 28,9
12	Toscana	☆ 26,1
13	Valle d'Aosta	☆ 25,8
14	Emilia-Romagna	☆ 25,2
15	Lombardia	☆ 25
16	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	☆ 22,3
17	Liguria	☆ 22,2
18	Veneto	☆ 19,8
19	Trentino-Alto Adige	☆ 15

Sedentarietà nelle Regioni Italiane nel 2020. Fonte: ISTAT-BES

Variazione Percentuale della Sedentarietà tra il 2005 ed il 2020

Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Campania</i>	★ -0,90	★ -1,58
2	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ -6,00	★ -9,58
3	<i>Calabria</i>	★ -7,10	★ -12,52
4	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ -7,30	★ -13,59
5	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ -3,70	★ -14,23
6	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ -6,50	★ -18,36
7	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	★ -3,50	★ -18,92
8	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ -8,70	★ -20,09
9	<i>Umbria</i>	★ -8,40	★ -20,10
10	<i>Molise</i>	★ -10,50	★ -20,39
11	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ -6,70	★ -21,00
12	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ -6,70	★ -21,14
13	<i>Marche</i>	★ -8,40	★ -22,52
14	<i>Veneto</i>	★ -6,00	★ -23,26
15	<i>Puglia</i>	★ -14,30	★ -25,31
16	<i>Lazio</i>	★ -11,50	★ -26,02
17	<i>Toscana</i>	★ -9,50	★ -26,69
18	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ -13,40	★ -34,18
19	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ -17,10	★ -35,55
20	<i>Liguria</i>	★ -19,20	★ -46,38

Variazione Assoluta della Sedentarietà tra il 2005 ed il 2020

Variatione Percentuale della Sedentarietà tra il 2005 ed il 2020

Regioni	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Piemonte	35,4	35,3	30,7	30,8	35	33,6	31,9	30	35,3	32,5	30,2	32,4	32,6	25,7	27,7	28,9
Valle d'Aosta	39,2	32,6	29,4	33,3	28,2	35,4	33,8	32	31,8	30,3	24,5	32,5	32,2	27,9	23,2	25,8
Liguria	41,4	33,6	42,1	40,6	38,9	39,2	41,4	34	41,7	36,3	34,4	36,6	32,3	31,2	31,4	22,2
Lombardia	31,7	32,7	34	31,9	35,7	30,3	31	31,7	34,1	29,7	31,6	30,7	29,3	27,1	25	25
Trentino-Alto Adige	18,5	18,1	15,8	16,3	17,5	14,6	15,6	15,7	15,7	17,8	13,9	15,6	16,6	15,2	12,9	15
Veneto	25,8	30,5	26,1	28,3	26,9	22,9	24,2	23,8	24,5	27,8	27,4	25,7	25,3	22,2	23,3	19,8
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	26	31,7	31,8	29,3	29,9	29,5	28,9	29,9	27,8	27,7	29,4	25,8	25,5	23,5	24,4	22,3
Emilia-Romagna	31,9	31,2	31,2	30,2	34,1	29,4	29,9	30,4	31,1	30,7	31	30,9	30,6	26,2	27,8	25,2
Toscana	35,6	37	34,5	36,4	38,2	29,7	36,3	35,9	36	33,2	33,3	32	30,3	28,2	30,5	26,1
Umbria	41,8	44,7	44,4	39,4	40,6	37,5	37,9	38,6	39,8	40,3	40	37,9	34,4	29,5	33	33,4
Marche	37,3	40,4	39,4	40,2	36,2	39,6	36,7	36,1	34,9	35	35,2	31,4	29,9	32,5	30,6	28,9
Lazio	44,2	45,6	42,2	46,8	45,4	41,1	46	44,8	44,3	43,3	43,9	41,6	40,6	39,6	39,6	32,7
Abruzzo	43,3	46,1	49,4	47,3	37,7	41,7	41	43,5	44,9	44,1	41,9	40,5	37,2	38,8	34,6	34,6
Molise	51,5	53,8	54	46,9	52,3	51,7	50,9	50,5	50,6	44,2	55,2	51,9	47,4	42,6	51,8	41
Campania	57,1	58	56,6	57,1	57	59,3	59,4	60,7	61,6	56,8	59,1	59,2	55,3	55,5	53,3	56,2
Puglia	56,5	53,5	55,7	52,3	55,1	50,9	58,2	53,2	54,8	57,1	52,3	51,4	49,2	45,8	43,7	42,2
Basilicata	53,7	53	50,1	47,7	49,1	49,1	48,7	48,5	52,5	52,5	52,1	50,6	46,7	45,4	51,6	46,4
Calabria	56,7	61	53,6	57,4	49,9	49,7	52,8	48,1	53,3	55,5	57,7	54,2	51,8	51,4	51,9	49,6
Sicilia	62,6	62,3	58,7	64,8	61,1	61,1	60,2	57,1	61,2	61,1	59,1	59	57,1	55,9	56,3	56,6
Sardegna	48,1	49,7	41,1	46,8	44,1	41,8	35,8	42,9	38,4	37,9	36,4	33,9	34,9	33,8	34,6	31
Nord	31,2	32	31,4	30,7	33	29,4	29,9	29,3	31,7	29,9	30	29,8	28,9	25,6	25,5	24,1
Centro	40,2	42,1	39,6	42,1	41,5	37	41	40,3	40,1	38,9	39,2	37,1	35,7	34,4	35,1	30,2
Mezzogiorno	56,4	56,7	54,6	56,2	54,3	54,2	55,1	54,1	56,1	55	54,4	53,5	51,1	50	49,2	49,1
Italia	41,9	42,7	41,2	41,8	42,1	39,5	40,8	40,1	41,8	40,4	40,2	39,4	37,9	35,7	35,5	33,8

Ranking degli algoritmi per efficienza produttiva						
Rank	Algoritmo	R ²	Mean absolute error	Mean squared error	Root mean squared error	Totale
1	Tree Ensemble Regression	★ 1 ★	1 ★	1 ★	1 ★	1 ★ 4
2	Gradient Boosted Trees Regression	★ 2 ★	2 ★	2 ★	2 ★	2 ★ 8
3	ANN-MLP	★ 3 ★	3 ★	3 ★	3 ★	3 ★ 12
4	PNN	☆ 4 ☆	5 ☆	5 ☆	5 ☆	4 ★ 18
5	Simple Regression Tree	☆ 5 ☆	4 ☆	4 ☆	4 ☆	5 ★ 18
6	Random Forest Regression	☆ 6 ☆	6 ☆	6 ☆	6 ☆	6 ★ 24
7	Polynomial Regression	☆ 7 ☆	7 ☆	7 ☆	7 ☆	7 ★ 28
8	Linear Regression	☆ 8 ☆	8 ☆	8 ☆	8 ☆	8 ★ 32

Valore della Predizione della Sedentarietà

	2020	Predizione	Variazione Assoluta	Variazione Percentuale
Valle d'Aosta	★ 25,80	★ 25,36	★ -0,44	★ -1,70
Lombardia	★ 25,00	★ 25,17	★ 0,17	★ 0,69
Veneto	★ 19,80	★ 23,43	★ 3,63	★ 18,33
Emilia Romagna	★ 25,20	★ 24,99	★ -0,21	★ -0,82
Campania	★ 56,20	★ 44,76	★ -11,44	★ -20,36
Sicilia	★ 56,60	★ 44,76	★ -11,84	★ -20,92
Media	★ 34,77	★ 31,41	★ -3,35	★ -9,65

Risultati Statistici della predizione attraverso l'utilizzo degli algoritmi di machine learning

Misure Statistiche	ANN-MLP	PNN	Simple Regression Tree	Gradient Boosted Trees Regression
R ²	0,843163999	0,76343339	0,759283149	0,982812171
Mean absolute error	0,102946502	0,135758153	0,123405709	0,036353605
Mean squared error	0,015947023	0,038494453	0,023347272	0,002511568
Root mean squared error	0,126281521	0,196200033	0,152798142	0,050115543
Misure Statistiche	Random Forest Regression	Tree Ensemble Regression	Linear Regression	Polynomial Regression
R ²	0,126944231	0,986414471	-2	-1
Mean absolute error	0,27487975	0,03606846	0,45596206	0,432038835
Mean squared error	0,097432962	0,002386565	0,338414634	0,315698935
Root mean squared error	0,312142534	0,048852486	0,581734161	0,561870924

